

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A fourth order orthogonal spline collocation method Interface boundary value problem

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Abstract

Objective: A higher order numerical scheme for two-point boundary interface problem with Dirichlet and Neumann boundary condition on two different sides is propounded. **Methods:** Orthogonal cubic spline collocation techniques have been used (OSC) for the two-point interface boundary value problem. To approximate the solution a piecewise Hermite cubic basis functions have been used. **Findings:** Remarkable features of the OSC are accounted for the numerous applications, theoretical clarity, and convenient execution. The stability and efficiency of orthogonal spline collocation methods over B-splines have made the former more preferable than the latter. As against finite element methods, determining the approximate solution and the coefficients of stiffness matrices and mass is relatively fast as the evaluation of integrals is not a requirement. The systematic incorporation of boundary and interface conditions in OSC adds to the list of advantages of preferring this method. **Novelty:** As against the existing methodologies it becomes clear from our findings that OSC is dominantly computationally superior. A computational treatment has been implemented on the two-point interface boundary value problem with super-convergent results of derivative at the nodal points, being the noteworthy finding of the study.

Keywords: Helmholtz problem; Orthogonal spline collocation techniques (OSC); Discontinuous data; Super Convergence; Piecewise cubic Hermite basis functions; Almost block diagonal (ABD) structure

1 Introduction

The 1D- Helmholtz equation under consideration is:

$$y'' + k^2 q(x)y = f(x), \quad x \in [a, b] \quad (1.1)$$

with boundary conditions

$$\alpha_a y(a) + \beta_a y'(a) = g_0, \quad \alpha_b y(b) + \beta_b y'(b) = g_1 \quad (1.2)$$

where $\alpha_a, \beta_a, \alpha_b, \beta_b, g_0, g_1$ are known constants and k^2 is the wave number. We assume the coefficient $q(x)$ to be piece-wise constant or piece-wise continuous with finite jump across the interface $x = x_i, x_i \in (a, b)$.

For convenience, we assume that $\omega^2 = k^2 q(x)$ which is a piece-wise constant or piece-wise continuous across the interface $x = x_i$, and assume that solution $y(x)$ satisfies the natural jump conditions across the interface $(y) = 0, (y') = 0$.

The jump conditions across the interface are:

$$[y]_{x=x_i} = \lim_{x \rightarrow x_i^+} y(x) - \lim_{x \rightarrow x_i^-} y(x) = y^+(x_i) - y^-(x_i).$$

Let

$$\pi : a = x_0 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_N < x_{N+1} = b$$

denote a partition of I , and set $I_j = (x_{j-1}, x_j], j = 1, \dots, N + 1, h_j = x_j - x_{j-1}$ and $h = \max_j h_j$.

The Helmholtz equation is used in many physical applications such as acoustics, elastic waves, and electromagnetic waves. The present study intends to provide an efficient numerical skill for Helmholtz problem.

Existing literature of theoretical and numerical treatment to Helmholtz equation using finite difference methods⁽¹⁻³⁾, finite element methods⁽⁴⁾ and for existence uniqueness results can be found at⁽⁵⁻⁷⁾. 1D and 2D Helmholtz equation have been treated by Xiufang Feng⁽⁸⁾ and Xiufang Feng et al.⁽⁹⁾ respectively by using high order compact finite difference methods.

This paper treats 1D-Helmholtz equation with piece-wise constant or piecewise continuous functions by employing OSC to it. The stability and efficiency of orthogonal spline collocation methods over B-splines have made the former more preferable than the latter. As against finite element methods, determining the approximate solution and the coefficients of stiffness matrices and mass is relatively fast as the evaluation of integrals is not a requirement. The systematic incorporation of boundary and interface conditions in OSC adds to the list of advantages of preferring this method.

We show that the OSC handle the interface conditions effectively with less discretization. To accomplish the fourth-order accuracy, we utilize piece-wise Hermite cubic basis functions for approximating the solution. This article can be outlined as: Section 2 uses OSC to approximate the solution. Section 3 deals with numerical experiments. Discontinuous data has been used and the solution has been approximated using piece-wise Hermite cubic basis functions. Grid refinement analysis is performed and the order of convergence for L^2 -norm and H^1 -norm is found. Section 4 hosts the conclusion.

2 Orthogonal spline collocation methods

Here, we employ OSC to approximate the solutions of interface boundary value problem (1.1).

Let

$$H^m(I) = \{v : v \in C^{m-1}(I) \text{ and } v^m \text{ is a piecewise continuous function on } I\},$$

with norm

$$\|v\|_{H^m(I)} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \|v_i\|_{L^2(I)}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where,

$$\|v\|_{L^2(I)} = \left(\int |v(x)|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \|v\|_{H^0(I)}.$$

Also set

$$H_0^1(I) = H^1 \cap \{(v|v(a) = v(b) = 0)\}.$$

Let

$$\pi : a = x_0 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{N-1} < x_N = b,$$

represents a partition of I , and set

$$I_j = (x_{j-1}, x_j], j = 1, 2, \dots, N, h_j = x_j - x_{j-1} \text{ and } h = \max_j h_j.$$

we assume that $x_i \in \pi$. In the OSC, the approximate solution, y_h , lies in a space C^1 piece-wise polynomials of degree ≥ 3 . Here we choose the space of piece-wise Hermite cubics, $M_1^3(\pi)$ as:

$$M_1^3(\pi) = \{(v|v \in C^1(I), (v|_{I_j} \in P_3, j = 1, 2, \dots, N)\},$$

3 Numerical experiments

In order to arrive at an approximate solution, piece-wise Hermite cubic basis functions will be considered for the experimentation and as for the determination of the order of convergence of the numerical method we will emphasize on grid refinement analysis.

The approximate solution $y_h(x) \in M_1^3$ on each subinterval $(x_{i-1}, x_i]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ is:

$$y_h(x) = \sum_{j=0}^N \{ \alpha_j v_j(x) + \beta_j s_j(x) \}, \tag{3.1}$$

where,

$$\alpha_j = y_h(x_j), \quad \beta_j = y'_h(x_j), \quad j = 0, \dots, N.$$

Since

$$v_j(x_i) = \delta_{ij}, \quad v'_j(x_i) = 0 \text{ and } s_j(x_i) = 0, \quad s'_j(x_i) = \delta_{ij}, \quad i, j = 0, \dots, N,$$

where δ_{ij} is the kronecker delta function with $\delta_{ij} = 1$, if $i = j$ and $\delta_{ij} = 0$, if $i \neq j$. The expressions for value functions and slope functions, we refer to⁽³⁾.

Taking derivatives of (3.1) wrt x, we have,

$$y'_h(x) = \sum_{j=0}^N \{ \alpha_j v'_j(x) + \beta_j s'_j(x) \}$$

and

$$y''_h(x) = \sum_{j=0}^N \{ \alpha_j v''_j(x) + \beta_j s''_j(x) \} \tag{3.2}$$

$(\xi_i)_{i=1}^{2N}$ are the collocation points on $(x_{i-1}, x_i]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ are two-point Gauss-Legendre quadrature points defined by

$$\xi_{2i-1} = x_{i-1} + \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right) h_i, \quad \text{and} \quad \xi_{2i} = x_{i-1} + \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right) h_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Now substituting equations (3.1) - (3.2) in (1.1) and the resulting equation, we calculate on $(x_{i-1}, x_i]$ at $x = \xi_1$, we get

$$\alpha_0 v''_0(\xi_1) + \beta_0 s''_0(\xi_1) + \alpha_1 v''_1(\xi_1) + \beta_1 s''_1(\xi_1) + \omega^2 \alpha_0 v_0(\xi_1) + \omega^2 \beta_0 s_0(\xi_1) + \omega^2 \alpha_1 v_1(\xi_1) + \omega^2 \beta_1 s_1(\xi_1) = f(\xi_1) \tag{3.3}$$

Similarly, at $x = \xi_2$ we have the following expression

$$\alpha_0 v''_0(\xi_2) + \beta_0 s''_0(\xi_2) + \alpha_1 v''_1(\xi_2) + \beta_1 s''_1(\xi_2) + \omega^2 \alpha_0 v_0(\xi_2) + \omega^2 \beta_0 s_0(\xi_2) + \omega^2 \alpha_1 v_1(\xi_2) + \omega^2 \beta_1 s_1(\xi_2) = f(\xi_2). \tag{3.4}$$

Let $x = x_i$ be the interface point on $I = (a, b)$. By observing equations (3.3) - (3.4) the collocation equations on the sub-intervals $[x_0, x_1], [x_1, x_2], \dots, [x_{i-1}, x_i]$, can be expressed in the matrix form as

$$A_i y_i + B_i y_{i+1} = f_i \tag{3.5}$$

where A_i and B_i structure out as:

$$A_i = \begin{pmatrix} v''_{i-1}(\xi_{2i-1}) + \omega^2 v_{i-1}(\xi_{2i-1}) & s''_{i-1}(\xi_{2i-1}) + \omega^2 s_{i-1}(\xi_{2i-1}) \\ v''_{i-1}(\xi_{2i}) + \omega^2 v_{i-1}(\xi_{2i}) & s''_{i-1}(\xi_{2i-1}) + \omega^2 s_{i-1}(\xi_{2i-1}) \end{pmatrix},$$

$$B_i = \begin{bmatrix} v''_i(\xi_{2i-1}) + \omega^2 v_i(\xi_{2i-1}) & s''_i(\xi_{2i-1}) + \omega^2 s_i(\xi_{2i-1}) \\ v''_i(\xi_{2i}) + \omega^2 v_i(\xi_{2i}) & s''_i(\xi_{2i-1}) + \omega^2 s_i(\xi_{2i-1}) \end{bmatrix}$$

f_i structures as $\begin{bmatrix} f_i^-(\xi_{2i-1}) \\ f_i^-(\xi_{2i}) \end{bmatrix}$ and $y_i = [\alpha_{i-1}, \beta_{i-1}]^T$, $y_{i+1} = [\alpha_i, \beta_i]^T$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$.

Table 1. L^∞ error for Example 1

N	$\omega^2 = 1, \omega^2 = 25$		$\omega^2 = 5, \omega^2 = 100$	
	–	order	–	order
8	2.2685e-01		5.5156e-02	
16	1.3846e-03	7.3561e+00	3.3897e-03	4.0243e+00
32	1.0897e-04	3.6674e+00	1.6551e-04	4.3562e+00
64	6.8095e-06	4.0003e+00	1.1538e-05	3.8424e+00
128	4.2561e-07	3.9999e+00	7.2997e-07	3.9824e+00
256	2.6628e-08	3.9985e+00	4.5619e-08	4.0001e+00

Table 2. L^∞ error of derivative for Example 1

N	$\omega^2 = 1, \omega^2 = 25$		$\omega^2 = 5, \omega^2 = 100$	
	–	order	–	order
8	3.3212e-01		8.6859e-02	
16	6.7995e-03	5.6102e+00	7.2906e-03	3.5746e+00
32	4.2674e-04	3.9940e+00	1.1388e-03	2.6786e+00
64	2.7118e-05	3.9761e+00	8.8430e-05	3.6868e+00
128	1.7192e-06	3.9794e+00	5.6226e-06	3.9752e+00
256	1.0749e-07	3.9994e+00	3.5136e-07	4.0002e+00

N.B: Since it is a numerical scheme, so the convergence depends upon the large value N. Initially it may get some deviation but at the higher value of N, it will converge to 4th order, which has been inferred from the above mentioned table.

Example 2: We consider the following problem

$$y''(x) + (p'(x)/p(x))y'(x) + (1/p(x))y(x) = f(x)/p(x), \quad x \in (-1, 1)$$

With boundary conditions i.e., Dirichlet on one side and Neumann on the other side

$$y(-1) = -\sin(1), \quad y'(1) = \cos(1),$$

where,

$$p(x) = \begin{cases} x, & x \in [-1, 0] \\ (1+x), & x \in [0, 1] \end{cases}$$

The exact solution is given by $y(x) = xsinx$.

The expression for $f(x)$ can be computed using $y(x) = xsinx$.

Table 3. L^∞ error of value and derivative for Example 2

N	$p_1 = x$		$p_2 = (1+x)$	
	–	order	–	order
8	1.4615e-05		1.1332e-05	
16	8.7474e-07	4.0624e+00	6.7401e-07	4.0714e+00
32	5.3506e-08	4.0311e+00	4.1092e-08	4.0358e+00
64	3.3080e-09	4.0157e+00	2.5361e-09	4.0182e+00
128	2.0561e-10	4.0079e+00	1.5749e-10	4.0092e+00
256	1.2815e-11	4.0040e+00	9.8099e-12	4.0049e+00

5 Conclusion

An OSC to 1D- Helmholtz equation with discontinuous coefficients has been established in the study. Discontinuous data has been experimented on, using numerical methodologies. Fourth-order convergence at the grid points for $\|y - y_h\|_{L^\infty}$ -norm

and $\|y' - y'_h\|_{L^\infty}$ -norm has been found. As against the methods that exist, OSC handles the discontinuous coefficients potently and gives optimal order of convergence for $\|y - y_h\|_{L^\infty}$ -norm and super-convergent result for $\|y - y_h\|_{L^\infty}$ -norm. Despite having theorized and having computed the OSC for a single point in the interface we can extend our theory to a finite set of points.

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